

The Tales of Series: Capturing the Players' Hearts (Part I)

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

Currently, the “Tales of saga”, or simply “Tales” as it is known in the West —“*Teiruzu Obu*” in Japan—, enjoys a large and devoted following. However, it did not always enjoy such fame outside the Japanese archipelago. In this article, we will recount the early years of development of this almost legendary Japanese role-playing game franchise, and how, despite the numerous obstacles it faced in reaching audiences beyond Japan, it managed to capture a piece of our hearts, ultimately amassing more than a dozen official titles.

In this article, we will focus primarily on the mainline games, and for reasons of length, not every aspect of the plot and characters of each title will be covered. Each *Tales of* video game features a subtitle known as the “Characteristic Genre”, which serves to distinguish each game from the rest, keeping them as original experiences despite the many shared elements.

***Tales of Phantasia*, the beginnings of the saga, and the unforgettable tragedy of Cless**

Back in 1995, Namco —currently Bandai Namco, following the merger of the two companies in 2005— released the first title in this franchise, developed by Wolf Team —also known as Wolfteam—, a studio born within the Japanese developer Telenet Japan —responsible for some versions of *Golden Axe*, among other titles, and which closed its doors in 2007—.

Wolfteam would later be renamed Namco Tales Studio. *Tales of Phantasia* became known for its Characteristic Genre, “Legendary RPG”.

The story of this video game was crafted by Yoshiharu Gotanda, who planned it as a novel that ultimately was never published, but which laid the groundwork for the game’s script. Gotanda was also the lead programmer and writer for the game, while the project was directed by Eiji Kikuchi —who would go on to direct the majority of the franchise’s subsequent titles.

Many changes had to be made to the original script, and levels and features were removed for technical reasons. The game was not initially accepted for publication by Enix, but Namco ultimately decided to support the project.

Drawing upon elements of Norse mythology, as well as popular European science fiction and horror stories to make the title more appealing to Western audiences —although it would not see release outside Japan until years later, forcing fans to import and play it in Japanese in the meantime—, the game begins with an impressive and memorable introduction, remarkable for what it represented technically at the time.

The game featured a vocal theme with lyrics, revolutionary for a home console such as the Super Famicom —SNES—. The opening theme is *The Dream will Never Die* —*Yume wa Owaranai*—, performed by Yukari Yoshida, while the audio accompanies the opening credits —which include a quote from one of the characters, Edward D. Morrison, whom we would learn more about later in the adventure— and several animated video sequences using sprites, showing key moments of the story while introducing the protagonists along with their seiyūs’ names.

The story then suddenly begins in earnest: four warriors are seen battling a powerful enemy, whom they eventually manage to seal with the help of two magical pendants, thus “ending the curse”. Twelve years later, we meet the true protagonist of the adventure, Cless Alvein —or Cress Albane—, who sets out hunting alongside his friend Chester Barklight. While hunting a massive boar, the alarm bell of their village suddenly rings, and both rush back, only to find it utterly destroyed, all inhabitants slaughtered by a horde of dark soldiers led by the malevolent captain, Mars Udole.

The four heroes facing evil Dhaos

Chester refuses to leave their village without burying his family and neighbours, and Cless decides to set out in search of help, as he has an uncle living in the city of Euclid. His uncle, however, betrays him, and Cless is imprisoned, from which he manages to escape with the aid of a dying woman, who passes away shortly afterwards. Cless also encounters Mint, a girl with great healing powers who becomes his new companion on the adventure, and he chooses not to reveal to her that the woman who helped him escape from his cell was, in fact, her mother.

Upon reuniting with Chester, the trio of heroes meets Tornix D. Morrison, who is revealed to be one of the four heroes who, in the past, sealed away a malevolent entity alongside Mint and Cless's parents. Tornix informs them that the pendants they no longer possess—which were taken from Mint and Cless by Mars—were the key to sealing Dhaos, a formidable enemy of humanity, and he departs swiftly for a mausoleum.

The trio decide to follow Tornix to the mausoleum, but they are unable to confront the power of Dhaos, who has been released by Mars, who foolishly demands that Dhaos grant him his power in exchange for his help. After being mercilessly slain by Dhaos, Mars falls, and Tornix chooses to use all the power he has left to save the lives of the protagonists, sending them back in time—one hundred years, to be exact—, although Chester decides to sacrifice himself and remain with Tornix to ensure that Cless and Mint escape alive.

Upon discovering that Mint and he have travelled to the past, and devastated by Chester's sacrifice, Cless wanders through this new world in which he and Mint have arrived, and is utterly astonished to find himself in a village that will later become his hometown—which at this point is not yet named Totus—. However, in this past world, they already encounter Dhaos, for one hundred years prior to Cless's era, the malevolent sorcerer was engaged in a war against all sentient races of the world.

The protagonists learn that only magic can harm the sorcerer, and this is a power that can be wielded only by those with elven blood. Consequently, they decide to travel the world in search of expert magic users to be able to defeat the Dark Lord. During their adventures, they befriend Klarth F. Lester—initially reluctant to help them, except in exchange for a considerable sum, which the protagonists could not hope to raise—, a twenty-nine-year-old human who has mastered magic through the power of summoning various elemental spirits, with whom he must establish a contractual relationship in order to harness their abilities.

Promotional art for *Tales of Phantasia* by Kōsuke Fujishima, used on the cover of the original 1995 video game.

They are soon joined by Arche Klaine, a cheerful young half-elf mage who, traumatised by the loss of her friend Rhea Scarlett, allows her spirit to possess her in order to take revenge on the sorcerer Demitel, a servant of Dhaos. After aiding Arche, Cless, Mint, and Klarth come to see her as a formidable ally against Dhaos, as well as a spirited and determined young woman. The group confronts Dhaos after assisting the kingdoms of Alvanista and Midgard in the war against him, and following a fierce battle, they manage to defeat him —although in truth Dhaos escapes. The protagonists then employ a time machine in the city of Thor, travelling just moments after Dhaos's escape with the aid of Tornix. Thanks to this, Chester and Tornix survive Dhaos's attack, who is eventually defeated...

...only for Dhaos to escape once more, this time into the future. Our heroes learn of this through a time traveller who has journeyed fifty years back to warn them that Dhaos is devastating their world. Using the time machine again, Cless and his team obtain the Eternal Sword, said to be the only weapon capable of preventing Dhaos from travelling through time. After finally vanquishing the villain, the team encounters the spirit Martel and discovers that, if Dhaos was cruel, his intentions had been noble, for the entire life of his planet —Derris-Kharlan— was on the verge of withering.

Dhaos sought to obtain a seed from the mana tree Yggdrasil to save his world, and, seeing how humans and half-elves used the power of mana thoughtlessly, causing destruction through the use of magitech —which drained the mana from Yggdrasil, causing it to wither—, he resolved to eliminate them all. The adventure concludes with Cless and his team deciding to help Martel save Dhaos's world. Mint creates a protective barrier around Yggdrasil, while Martel manages to produce a seed to restore the planet Derris-Kharlan.

One of the hallmarks of this video game, which would continue throughout the rest of the saga, was its high-quality soundtrack, composed in this case by the likes of Motoi Sakuraba, Shinji Tamura, and Ryōta Furuya. The work of the artist and mangaka Kōsuke Fujishima, who would also continue contributing to the saga over the years, either alone or in collaboration with other artists, is also noteworthy. The game also featured gameplay mechanics that were quite innovative for the time. Being an RPG, its combat system did not rely on traditional turns; rather, when characters encounter an enemy, the screen shifts from a top-down view to a side-on perspective, allowing players to control characters in real time from left to right.

The protagonist is always controlled directly, but the player can issue commands to the rest of the team manually, or leave them under the control of the game's AI, with several options available for this purpose. This approach to battles is known as the *Linear Motion Battle System*, which would become one of the Tales of series' signature features.

Each instalment of the series would also feature a story in which, much like other major RPG franchises such as Dragon Quest or Final Fantasy, each iteration presents an original narrative, rather than following the same characters across multiple titles—although this rule is occasionally broken, and connections can exist between different entries in all of these franchises, including Tales. Another notable feature is the existence of “recipes”: items that can be created by combining others, such as various foods that gradually restore the party's health when consumed.

Tales of arrives on PlayStation

Tales of Phantasia was later adapted for PlayStation in 1998, PlayStation Portable in 2006, and Game Boy Advance—a version released in Japan in 2003—. This version was finally playable officially in English language in 2006, though it was technically inferior to the original or the PlayStation versions. It offered the possibility of adding another character to the team, the ninja Suzu Fujibayashi on PlayStation, who was also available on Game Boy Advance. *Phantasia* even received an animated OVA adaptation in 2004, with the participation of artist Tokuyuki Matsutake, whom the CoolJapan.es team met at the Salón del Manga in Murcia and interviewed.

Following the success of *Tales of Phantasia*, Wolf Team set to work and released *Tales of Destiny* in 1997, the first title in the franchise to be published in a language other than Japanese—the English-language version was released in 1998—. It later received a remake for PlayStation 2 in 2006 and a Director's Cut in 2008, also for PlayStation 2. All versions share an animated opening sequence produced by Production I.G. *Tales of Destiny* carried the Characteristic Genre subtitle “Fateful RPG”.

The story begins when the protagonist, Stahn Aileron, seeking adventure, stows away on a ship called *Draconis*. The crew discovers him and forces him to work to pay for his passage, but Stahn manages to escape when the ship is suddenly caught in battle against enemy forces. In search of a weapon for defence, Stahn acquires a talking sword named Dymlos, which can wield the element of fire and claims to be part of a group called “Swordian” from the past Aeth'er Wars. Stahn is the archetypal headstrong protagonist who quickly wins the player's affection.

In the past, a comet struck the game world's planet, rendering it a near-uninhabitable wasteland. The survivors discovered a source of power within the comet in the form of a mineral called "Lens", which served as a new energy source. They even managed to construct floating cities, although only Dycroft was completed successfully. Not all humans could live in this Aeropolis, and the world population was divided between the Aetherians and the E'rthers —the latter being those who continued living on the planet's surface or interior. The Aetherians possessed a weapon called Belcrant, which ensured their dominance over those living on the surface or interior for many years.

Disillusioned by the Aetherians' treatment of the E'rthers, the scientists abandoned the Aetherians and developed the Swordians to aid the latter, including the sword found by Stahn.

Throughout his adventure, Stahn is joined by other characters —with character designs by Mutsumi Inomata— such as Rutee Katrea, who develops a romantic relationship with him, Leon Magnus, who ultimately betrays the party and is executed, and Mary Argent and Bruiser Khang. It is these relationships that enrich the RPG and gradually reveal its story, which begins in a relatively conventional manner.

Screenshot of the original *Tales of Destiny*, in its US version

Following *Destiny* came *Tales of Eternia* in 2000, which received its US release in 2001, also for PlayStation. Initially, it was titled *Tales of Destiny II* in the United States, in order to market the game to North American audiences by conveying a sense of continuity.

The game marked a significant leap for the series, incorporating voiced audio sequences for the various scenes, performed by the voice actors of each character, and also featured dubbing in the English-language version. In 2004, it received a PlayStation Portable release. *Eternia* carries the Characteristic Genre subtitle “Eternity and Bonds RPG”.

At a time when three-dimensional polygon graphics were becoming fashionable, Namco and Wolf Team chose to continue using a mix of pre-rendered backgrounds with characters and elements created from sprites and animated sequences, both emulating the anime aesthetic for the Tales series. Once again, traditional-style animation was handled by Production I.G.

The story follows the young hunter Reid Hershel, from a small village, who grew up alongside the farmer and martial artist Farah Oersted and the apprentice mage Keele Zeibel. Reid encounters Meredy, a native of another planet, which is destined to be destroyed along with Reid’s world and those of his friends by a catastrophic event called “the Grand Fall”. Together, they resolve to fight to save both worlds, setting the stage for players to embark on a new odyssey.

The protagonist of *Tales of Eternia*, Reid Hershel —left—, alongside Farah Oersted —centre— and Meredy —right—. Image from the original 2000 PlayStation version of *Tales of Eternia*.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Domenech Alcaide, Andrés (2017), *Los videojuegos como producto del arte: La influencia e importancia del dibujo, del cómic y otras artes en su historia* (Doctoral thesis), University of Granada, Granada | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]

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